

Contextualising Dalit Discourse: Countering the Mainstream Casteist Narrative

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Abstract

The paper begins by examining the broader societal context in which Dalit culture and resistance arise. This context is characterized by the Brahmanical social order, which seeks to maintain its dominant position by perpetuating cultural inequalities rooted in unequal distributions of power and knowledge. The paper argues that Dalits can reclaim power and knowledge by challenging the production of Brahmanical cultural knowledge within the framework of the "politics of location". Furthermore, the paper endeavours to de-brahmanise the entrenched disciplinary space by introducing the narrative of the Dalit experience through Dalit Literature with caste and humiliation into the purview of mainstream academia. Dalit Literature include texts which act as discourse(knowledge) making tool for Dalits, and thus by delving into these complex interrelationships between texts and discourse, the author provides a nuanced and insightful analysis of the sociocultural dynamics that shape and influence the lived experiences of marginalized groups in India. By embracing Dalit perspectives and dismantling the Brahmanical dominance in cultural and academic spheres, the paper argues that a more horizontal and participatory approach to knowledge production can be achieved, leading to a more diverse and pluralistic body of knowledge.

Keywords: dalit discourse, dalit literature, anti-caste, politics of location.

“Dalit”: Mapping the Meaning

India, a vast and diverse country, is home to approximately one-sixth of the world's population, with a total population of 1.4 billion (UN DESA, 2023). Social and political organizations in India are greatly influenced by various factors, including religion, caste, and language. The pervasive caste system, deeply embedded in the psyche of Indian citizens of all socio-cultural backgrounds like Dalits, Brahmins, OBCs, affects many aspects of life both covertly as well as overtly. Despite putting great efforts to address this social bane, the caste system continues to play a significant role in Indian society. This system has been deeply ingrained in Indian culture and society for centuries and dictates a person's social status and opportunities based on birth. The caste system has had a disproportionate impact on Dalits in India, who historically have been considered "untouchable" and excluded from many aspects of society and politics. They are considered *varna-sankara*—“outside the caste system”. They are often the most vulnerable and economically disadvantaged, being among the poorest of the poor. Dalits are identified with different nomenclatures in different parts of India. The literal meaning of the term Dalit comes closest to the “word broken/ scattered”. The oppressed, crushed and dominated categories of people have been called as Dalit (Ramabadran & Paswan, 2021). Jyotiba Phule, a reverend social worker (1827-1890), introduced the term “*dalitodhar*”, meaning upliftment of the oppressed, as a counter to Brahmin oppression of lower castes, during his Satya Shodhak (Truth Seeking) movement. This term was subsequently adopted as an identifier for the Dalit community, as it encapsulates the essence of their experiences: oppression, powerlessness, internalization, and realization. The term effectively unites all Dalits, including those who have yet to recognize their oppressed state, thereby promoting a sense of solidarity among a historically divided and oppressed community (Ramabadran & Paswan, 2021). The word Dalit represents a means of acknowledging and accepting the true nature of the individual and their place in society. Rather than shying away from their experiences, the term, in essence, provides an autonomous and authentic acceptance of the

Dalit community's true identity. It serves as a political coinage that enables them to protect and promote their own identity. Despite its significance, the Dalit community continues to search for a more secular, liberated, and stigma-free identity, which remains a profound and poignant aspect of their existential reality.

Dalit Discourse: Identity, Power and Politics

To empower the Dalit community, it is crucial to dismantle the psychological barriers that hinder them from believing in the possibility of positive change. Efforts towards achieving change necessitates a shift in the "order of discourse," thus opening up the possibility of thinking and seeing reality through a different perspective. The Foucauldian Discourse is an exemplar of fields where the term "Discourse" is not only considered a count noun but is used to refer to a broad range of linguistic and non-linguistic social practices and ideological presuppositions that conspire to create and sustain power structures, politics, and culture. The term is socially constitutive and conditioned, possessing the ability to reproduce, legitimize, enact, resist, and negotiate power, reality, and ideology. It is crucial to harness and thoroughly understand the power of language and the myriad ways in which it constructs reality to advance the Dalit community's agenda of socio-political empowerment. By adopting an inclusive, discursive approach, it is possible to engage and ultimately transform the social, political, and ideological constructs that perpetuate social inequalities and oppression within the Dalit community and beyond.

The pioneers of the caste movement, including B.R. Ambedkar, Jotirao Phule, Periyar, and others, sought to deconstruct the deeply entrenched Brahmanical culture and knowledge-production to achieve their fundamental goal of integrating Dalits into the national mainstream socio-political discourse. The functioning of a democratic nation presupposes the active participation of every social stratum in the process of nation-building, including deliberation and discourse-making. In his seminal work, *Annihilation of Caste* (1936), Ambedkar revolutionarily proclaimed that the production of knowledge is monopolized by the mainstream, nationalist, elite, and legitimate public intellectuals - who happen to mostly be upper-caste Hindus.

Jotirao Phule, through his power and knowledge discourse, delineated the organized and controlled system of Brahmanical power and its exploitation of the *shetji-bhatji* (bania-brahmin) nexus. The upper-caste Brahmins have, through the manipulation of privileged knowledge production, maintained their status quo as the "top of the twice-born." Consequently, the deconstruction of the Brahmanical knowledge model is necessary to effect fundamental changes in Indian society, allowing for the full inclusion and participation of all members, particularly those marginalized and oppressed. By dismantling the structures and power dynamics that elevate the Brahmins and exclude other social groups, such as the Dalits, from the national socio-political discourse, it is possible to foster and maintain a more just, inclusive, and democratic nation.

[...]if experience and knowledge are inextricably interlinked in social sciences, then the location of the knowledge producer, the researcher, in social structure is crucial from the perspective of production of knowledge. That is, the perspective from below is necessitated due to the politics of location. The process of production of knowledge and the advantages emanating out of one's location in social structure are invariably linked. (Kumar, 2014).

The author supports Foucault's assertion that truth is not external to power, nor is it devoid of power – it is intrinsically linked to the form of discourse and the institution that produces it, as well as the political and economic role it serves. Consequently, the ascendance of a "symbolic truth" is produced and constantly disseminated by the ruling discourse. We now

find ourselves in an era of symbolism, where the symbolic has grown more vital than the truth it represents. That which can captivate and simultaneously desensitize the imagination (rendering it non-critical), holds the potential to maintain the status quo. The symbolic "truth" about the Dalits operates in much the same way; society perpetuates an ideology which results in Dalits coming to internalize their lowly position and view themselves as untouchable and inferior. As a result, they remain subject to social and economic oppression. The symbolic representation of their status and the discourse surrounding it serve to sustain the caste system by controlling and subjugating the oppressed. It is essential to recognize and deconstruct this symbolic truth to combat the perpetuation of such oppressive systems. By doing so, we can create a more equitable and inclusive society where all people have the opportunity to thrive and reach their full potential, free from social and economic constraints.

The emergence of identity politics has rendered symbolism a crucial tactic for political action. While it has successfully championed the rights of marginalized communities, it has also led to an overreliance on symbolism, masking the truth under layers of symbolic representation. In response, it becomes imperative to re-tell stories in ways that open new subject positions that can accommodate narratives of fear that shape politics in the years to come. However, attempts to rewrite history in contemporary India through measures such as renaming roads and towns have shifted attention from an egalitarian future to changing the way in which the past is conceptualized. This approach is detrimental to the Dalits and runs the risk of further entrenching their subordination. In order to ensure a more equitable future for all, it is vital to break free from the constraints of majoritarian symbolism and embrace dissenting voices. This will create space for truly transformative conversations that can lead to a future where the hierarchies of the past are dismantled, leading to a society where all individuals can thrive and reach their full potential. By dismantling the politics of fear and oppression, we can create a future where difference is celebrated, and all voices are heard and respected.

The phenomenon of caste has roots in the gripping religious system of Hinduism. The scriptural justification for labelling Dalits as untouchable, impure, and evil has further alienated them from the broader social construct. Moreover, the doctrine of relative purity, as espoused in various Hindu scriptures such as Manusmriti, has penetrated the Indian psyche and led to objectification and misrepresentation of the Dalit community. Manusmriti equates the Shudra caste with the dirt beneath the feet of Brahma, imbuing it with a lowly and impure connotation (*The Rig Veda*, 1896) This demeaning portrayal casts the Shudra as an individual who is only atoning for past-life mistakes, perpetuating the notion that their lowly status is earned by their previous incarnations. Such discriminatory attitudes and beliefs have profound consequences on the oppressed members of society and are a cause for concern in modern times.

The stories of the usurpation of power by a numerical minority and the resulting oppression of the masses are similar across different cultures. Examples include the rise of the Nazis and the Jewish domination of Palestinian territories. In the demographic context of India, the Brahmins constitute the privileged minority. However, there is a strategic effort to limit their numbers by imposing hypocritical standards of "Brahmanical purity", which are determined by the smaller number of individuals in a particular line of Brahmins, such as the Shakadwitya Brahmins and the Namboodri Brahmins from Kerala (*Kerala's Namboothiri Brahmins*, 2015).

When we look at the history of Dalit activism in India, there is one issue that has constantly plagued the way that activism is performed. It has often fallen prey to tokenism of the kind that prevents real ground-level change from happening and saturates itself at the level of ideologies (Prakash, 2021). Tokenism refers to a superficial approach to addressing social issues, where actions are taken only to create an appearance of progress rather than to effect

real change. This can hinder the effectiveness of activism and limit its impact on the ground, preventing actual progress and improvements in the lives of marginalized communities. Tokenism in Dalit activism can manifest in different ways. For instance, it can involve the use of symbolic gestures and empty promises, that lack clear mechanisms of implementation. This kind of tokenism is characterized by a focus on surface-level changes, such as increasing the number of Dalits in government jobs, while failing to address the underlying systemic barriers that prevent Dalits from accessing such positions in the first place (Thorat & Thorat, 2022)

Another manifestation of tokenism in Dalit activism occurs when non-Dalit individuals or organizations dominate the movement and do not give the space and resources for the voices of Dalit activists and organizations to be heard (Jaoul, 2008) This silences Dalit perspectives and undermines the efficacy of the movement, as non-Dalit actors may lack the nuanced insights and first-hand experiences of discrimination faced by the Dalit community. The issue of tokenism also ties into the broader problem of performative activism, where individuals and groups engage in activism primarily for the purpose of signalling their own moral righteousness, rather than actually working towards concrete change. Such performative activism is marked by a focus on appearances, and can result in the side-lining of marginalized voices, including those of the Dalit community. To overcome these challenges, it is essential to involve Dalit activists and organizations in the design and implementation of any efforts aimed at improving the conditions of the community. Additionally, non-Dalit individuals and organizations must recognize their own privilege and work towards creating a more inclusive space for marginalized voices to be heard.

It is impossible to think of a situation where the dalit individual is bereft of the genuine desires that their community has long held. These desires are connected on the level of the community and can be called “communal” existential desires (Blattner, 2012) These desires are in a way formative of the people that are central to the lives of the Dalits. However, it is also true that Dalit individuals may be influenced by the desires of their community and the collective experiences of the Dalit people as a whole. For instance, a Dalit individual may share the desire for social justice and equality that is central to the Dalit community's struggle against caste oppression. This shared desire can create a sense of solidarity and common purpose that strengthens the community's collective action to resist discrimination and marginalization.

Dalit Studies: Revolutionizing Knowledge Production and Cultivating Cultural Emancipation

Ankit Kawade (2019) mentions that Dalit Studies become an undesirable site for research because it is undervalued to retain the Brahmanical academic “purity” for their institutional disciplines. This hampers the free, unbiased, and plural flow of knowledge. The issue of caste-based inequalities is far-reaching and not limited to problems with institutional access. It extends to the status of the knowledge that is propagated, produced, and legitimized within these institutional spaces. This raises a crucial question regarding the content and sources of knowledge - whether they are representative and inclusive of diverse perspectives, or rooted in entrenched biases and narrow cultural narratives that reinforce caste-based inequality. To the global intelligentsia, this should read like the Derridian nightmare. This capture of the sources of knowledge is not a linear one-sided approach. Metaphorically and realistically, anonymity and ignominy are not the exceptions but the rule in the dominant social order and the dominant academic discourse where the Dalits are kept at the periphery (Kawade, 2019).

The emergence of "Dalit Studies" as a distinct field of inquiry is primarily a response to the systematic and pervasive negation of Dalit intellectuality. This negation is a crucial element of Brahmanism's operational functioning in society at large. In this sense, the rise of Dalit studies is an attempt to disrupt this pattern of oppression and restore the dignity and value of

Dalit knowledge and perspectives. However, despite the critical importance of this field, it is often considered undesirable or lesser in comparison to other fields of study. This negative perception is not merely a result of individual choice or preference, but rather is tied to broader politics of knowledge-production. The deliberate use of the term "knowledge-production" carries significant implications regarding the processes that enable knowledge dissemination. The mechanisms of corporate publishing and state-funded grants hold considerable political power, and these avenues of knowledge dissemination often come with their own complexities and intricacies. Unfortunately, this reality has led some to view the rise of Dalit studies as merely a cynical attempt to capitalize on a new academic trend. The commercialization of knowledge production creates a risk that the study of Dalit perspectives will become a mere commodity, traded in the academic marketplace for profit rather than a critical pursuit of knowledge that fosters meaningful social change. The prevailing cynicism surrounding Dalit studies portrays it as merely a lucrative opportunity, serving the academic circles rather than a social or political end. However, this view is misguided and detracts from the significance and relevance of Dalit studies in contemporary academic discourse. Dalit studies are an essential and critical field of study that has emerged to fill the void created by the exclusion and marginalization of Dalit perspectives from mainstream academic discourse. Thus, the commercialization and politicization of knowledge production should not undermine the significance and potential of Dalit studies as a transformative framework of social and political activism. It is crucial to uphold the integrity and authenticity of Dalit studies while resisting the market-driven tendencies that undermine its relevance and social significance. Embracing the transformative potential of Dalit studies can foster meaningful progress towards achieving social justice and equity.

The predominance of dominant cultural ideologies tends to marginalize and invalidate alternative perspectives, including those of Dalit studies. This invalidation results in the devaluation of Dalit epistemologies, which can create negative and undervalued epistemic status for the field. Guru's thought-provoking article, titled "*How Egalitarian Are the Social Sciences in India?*" (2002), is a scathing critique of the deeply ingrained cultural hierarchy that permeates the Indian social science research landscape. Through his analysis of the role of theory in the professional and social lives of marginalized groups, Guru highlights the pernicious dichotomy that pits empirical and theoretical research against each other. Drawing comparisons to the insidious caste-based system in India, Guru boldly argues that this division serves to devalue empirical research and entrench the dominance of the theoretical research elite, thereby perpetuating existing power structures within the social science field. There is a need for the inclusion of Dalit aesthetics in the mainstream cultural production and circulation of discourse. This discourse of Dalit experience of caste and humiliation in mainstream academia as well as mainstream society will attempt to de-brahmanise the established disciplinary and public space.

Dalit literature exposes what Dalit politics does not - the subtlety and widespread experience of caste discrimination, not only amongst the Dalit poor, but in the Dalit urban middle class. In other words, Dalit literature highlights the inescapability of caste identity and the emotionality of discrimination in a different way to Dalit politics. (Hunt, 2014).

This in no way means that the higher castes are free from their social responsibility. This also includes opening up places of privileged institutional education to not just the physical but the discursive presence of the Dalits. The current socio-political scenario in India looks absolutely averse to this expected course of community reform that is the need of the hour.

It is important to understand that Dalit Literature encompasses far more than just an exploration of the experiences of individuals or communities. It represents a unique "perspective from below," a mode of assertion or resistance that aims to challenge the brahmanical spaces that perpetuate knowledge disparities (Kumar, 2019). This perspective is distinctly different from the Lalit literature, which portrays the social reality through a superficial mirror image and prioritizes aesthetics over substance (Kumar, 2019). In contrast, Dalit Literature delves deeper and uncovers the "hidden truth" of mainstream society, revealing the innermost struggles and aspirations of the Dalit community. This is akin to an ultrasound image, which provides a glimpse beneath the surface and exposes the truths that lie within (Limbale, 2004). Ultimately, Dalit Literature is a tool for de-brahmanising the narrative of knowledge production and establishing the voices and experiences of the oppressed at the centre of cultural discourse. By shifting the focus to these marginalized perspectives, we can gain a greater understanding of society as a whole and work towards creating a more just and inclusive future for all.

Conclusion

The assertion made in the paper posits that to apprehend the problems that beset Dalits at the grassroots level, it is crucial to adopt an ethical approach to the liberated, existentially aware, and critical self. The verity regarding Dalits is safeguarded by the superstructure of meta-discourse, which has disrupted and perpetuated the disordered social order. Layers of symbolism encompassing reality place greater emphasis on the process over the consequences. Thus, a deconstructive reading of the Indian social order is necessary to discern the persistent marginalization of Dalits. According to Heidegger, the act of contemplating what deserves attention is an issue of great dignity because it allows for recognition and appreciation of the worth of that which is being encountered. Heidegger contends that by thinking about something, we are initially uncovering its concealed dignity. In the context of Dalit discourse, Dalit politics, and Dalit literature, the goal is to provide a path toward resolving the "double-bind" (Das, 2017) between affirmation and transcendence that exists within the Dalit experience. This issue regarding the intrinsic worth of the Dalit experience is pivotal to the study of Dalit studies, whose "concealed dignity" has been disregarded for a prolonged period within academic discourse. This involves the decentralization of dominant cultural narratives and the sharing of marginal voices. To this end, the paper is dedicated to dismantling the entrenched disciplinary space that is under the influence of Brahmanism. Taken together, these interconnected arguments highlight the underlying effects of a deeply flawed social order and the importance of recognizing and reconceptualising the narratives that give rise to structural oppression. Nevertheless, since this emancipated world is still yet to exist, we can find the relevance of Dalit discourse, literature, and politics in the present day. These realms exist about the ideal future world, encouraging both academic and political thought that pursue the common pursuit of correcting injustice and inequality in our world.

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